

NUMERICAL FORMULATION OF THE EVOLUTIVE ANISOTROPIC BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE FABRICS IN ORDER TO SIMULATE FORMING PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with a numerical model for the mechanical behaviour of non polymerised pre impregnated woven fabrics in order to simulate forming processes. The present formulation corresponds to the objective rigid-body rotation frame with an up-dating of the warp and weft yarn directions of the fabric. The hypothesis is assumed that the evolution of these directions is quasi-identical to the evolution of the principal directions of strain. The constitutive equations of the fabric behaviour are identified at each increment. The numerical model is integrated in the ABAQUS finite element software. Firstly we have studied the simple shear test with different orientations of the fabric. In a second part we have simulated an example of stamping.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of composite materials over the last few decades, more particularly in the field of aerospace, has implied the improvement of design rules and consequently, has lead the industries to look into the automation of the different manufacturing processes. In the case of automation of the classical laying up forming process, specific automated machines have been now in use for several years in different countries such as U.S.A., or France. But they were originally designed for developable or slightly undevelopable composite parts. In the case of undevelopable parts, automation was generally not considered. Several kinds of different systems in processing aids were achieved without taking various mechanical aspects of the fabric into account.

The present study is concerned with a general research pattern pertaining to the definition of the mechanical behaviour of prepreg fabrics used for the manufacture of undevelopable composite parts by laying-up as well as its extension for the stamping process.

Generally, two different approaches can be used for this type of problems : one way favours the geometrical aspect of the warping, the other one its mechanical aspect. Our research is based on the mechanical approach.

The behaviour of prepreg fabrics with resin in the non-polymerized phase during the manufacture of undevelopable composite parts by lay-up, depends on various parameters which can be grouped into two sets as :

- a) the parameters associated to the dry fabric
 - materials constituting warp and weft yarns (type and mechanical characteristics)
 - the method of preparation of the yarn (size, thickness, section shape, etc...)
 - the weaving technique (fabric weave, fabric structure)
- b) the parameters associated to the resin
 - the average resin content
 - the mechanical characteristics
 - the fabric impregnation method.

These parameters were identified experimentally after carrying out a whole range of mechanical tests, on the prepreg fabric, and the resin, separately and respectively.

A micro-structural finite element model developed earlier [1] was validated by comparing it to the results obtained from tests. This study has brought out that the most important factor for the shaping process is the fabric ability to allow for a relative rotation of the yarns associated with the plane shear of the resin [2].

In this paper, we present a finite element formulation based on anisotropic hypoelastic constitutive equations. This formulation has been achieved by considering the need to obtain an industrial design tool. We have also developed a macro-mechanical model, which substitutes an homogeneous continuous material to the discrete nature of fabric. The homogenisation has been obtained through an iteration in the computation procedure.

The continuous variation of the geometric positions of fabric yarns is taken into account by incorporating the velocity of particles in the formulation, thus allowing the evolution of anisotropy during the transformation. We have used Green-Nadghi's formulation associated with rigid body rotation derived from polar decomposition. The evolution of the orthotropic hypoelastic law is there determined by the location of the bisectors of the warp and weft directions identified at each instant of the transformation.

PRELIMINARIES

KINEMATICS OF THE TRANSFORMATION

Let us consider the motion of the different material points, called particles, of a deformable body. The motion of a particle P relative to a reference frame \mathcal{R} , associated to a orthonormal basis in a Euclidean space of three dimensions, is described by the time locus of its position vector $\mathbf{x}(P, t)$. This locus is the path trajectory of P in \mathcal{R} . This particle can be identified by its position vector $\mathbf{X}(P)$ in \mathcal{R} at a reference time (t_0). At this time the different particles occupy the reference configuration $\mathcal{C}(t_0)$ or \mathcal{C}_0 . The motion of this particle P is described by the vector function :

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{X}, t)$$

The position of different particles at a given time (t) corresponds to the current configuration $\mathcal{C}(t)$ or \mathcal{C} .

The transformation of an infinitesimal element $d\mathbf{X}$ in \mathcal{C}_0 into an infinitesimal element $d\mathbf{x}$ in \mathcal{C} , is defined by the *deformation gradient* tensor \mathbf{F} .

$$d\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{F}.d\mathbf{X}$$

This tensor which is continuously differentiable has a strictly-positive determinant, and hence admits the polar decomposition

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{R}.\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{V}.\mathbf{R}$$

$\mathbf{U}(t)$ and $\mathbf{V}(t)$ describe the local deformation of the element and are referred to as the right and left stretch tensor respectively. These tensors are symmetric and positive-definite. $\mathbf{R}(t)$ is the proper orthogonal tensor and characterises the rigid body rotation with $\mathbf{R}^T = \mathbf{R}^{-1}$.

The material time rate of change of the body deformation is described by the velocity gradient tensor \mathbf{L} .

$$\mathbf{L} = \text{grad } \dot{\mathbf{x}} = \dot{\mathbf{F}} \cdot \mathbf{F}^{-1}$$

The symmetric part \mathbf{D} is called the stretching tensor,

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{sym } \mathbf{L} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{L}^T)$$

and the anti symmetric part \mathbf{W} the spin tensor,

$$\mathbf{W} = \text{skw } \mathbf{L} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{L} - \mathbf{L}^T)$$

This completes the sketch of basic kinematics essential for this presentation.

CHANGE OF FRAME AND OBJECTIVITY

For pure homogeneous deformations, an orthogonal triad, composed of the principal axes which remain orthogonal throughout the deformation, can be identified. Furthermore, its material derivative equals the deformation rate tensor. Only for homogeneous (not pure) deformations is the deformation gradient tensor unsymmetric, and there is no triad which remains orthogonal throughout. For this reason, finite strain formulations which involve stress rate must compensate for the material rotation by using objective derivatives [5], [6]. These objective derivatives are divided into two types : the convective derivatives and those which eliminate the parasitic rotations by changing frame. For the latter, a lot of objective tensor rates are proposed in literature.

Let $\{e_i(t)\}$ be a smooth, time-dependent orthonormal basis. The corresponding twirl tensor Ω is the skew tensor function defined by

$$\dot{e}_i = \Omega \cdot e_i$$

Given a smooth tensor function \mathbf{B} , the time derivative of \mathbf{B} measured by an observer rotating with $\{e_i(t)\}$ can be written as

$$\overset{\nabla}{\mathbf{B}} = \dot{\mathbf{B}} + \mathbf{B} \cdot \Omega - \Omega \cdot \mathbf{B}$$

Green-Nagdhi's (Mc Innis or Dienes) derivative corresponds to the case of $\{e_i(t)\}$ associated with the rotation experienced by the material yarns and coinciding with the principal directions of strain since the initial time.

Sowerby-Chou's (Hill) derivatives corresponding to the case of $\{e_i(t)\}$ are the rotations of the principal directions of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} tensors,

Another important notion is Jaumann's derivative $\overset{J}{\mathbf{B}}$ given by

$$\overset{J}{\mathbf{B}} = \dot{\mathbf{B}} + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{W} - \mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{B}$$

in which \mathbf{W} is the spin. This derivative corresponds [4] to the corotational frame where, for each time, the materials yarns that coincide with the principal axes of deformation have no angular velocity.

APPLICATION TO A NON UP-DATED BEHAVIOUR LAW FOR SIMPLE SHEAR

The simple shear test can be described by the figure below :

Figure 1. Simple shear test

A Green-Nagdhi's formulation is used with an orthotropic hypoelastic behaviour law. The orthotropic axes are assumed to rotate with the rigid body frame. The overbars and greek subscripts denote the writing of equations in the rotating frame.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\bar{\sigma}}_{\alpha\alpha} \\ \dot{\bar{\sigma}}_{\beta\beta} \\ \dot{\bar{\sigma}}_{\alpha\beta} \end{Bmatrix} = [\bar{C}_{\alpha\beta}] \cdot [\dot{\bar{D}}] = \begin{bmatrix} C_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha} & C_{\alpha\alpha\beta\beta} & 0 \\ C_{\beta\beta\alpha\alpha} & C_{\beta\beta\beta\beta} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{\alpha\beta\alpha\beta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{D}_{\alpha\alpha} \\ \bar{D}_{\beta\beta} \\ 2\bar{D}_{\alpha\beta} \end{Bmatrix} \text{ with } \bar{D}_{\alpha\beta,3} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\dot{a}}{2} \sin(2\theta) & \frac{\dot{a}}{2} \cos(2\theta) & 0 \\ \frac{\dot{a}}{2} \cos(2\theta) & -\frac{\dot{a}}{2} \sin(2\theta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

and $\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{-a}{2}\right) + \theta_0$, θ_0 represents the initial angle (e_1, e_α) between the shearing direction and one of the orthotropic directions. The integration of these equations in the rotating local basis gives

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{\alpha\alpha}^R &= -\bar{\sigma}_{\beta\beta}^R = (C_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha} - C_{\alpha\alpha\beta\beta}) \cdot \left[\left(2 \arctan\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) - \frac{a}{2} \right) \cdot \sin(2\theta_0) - \ln\left(1 + \frac{a^2}{4}\right) \cdot \cos(2\theta_0) \right] \\ \bar{\sigma}_{\beta\beta}^R &= (C_{\alpha\alpha\beta\beta} - C_{\beta\beta\beta\beta}) \cdot \left[\left(2 \arctan\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) - \frac{a}{2} \right) \cdot \sin(2\theta_0) - \ln\left(1 + \frac{a^2}{4}\right) \cdot \cos(2\theta_0) \right] \\ \bar{\sigma}_{\alpha\beta}^R &= 2C_{\alpha\beta\alpha\beta} \cdot \left[\left(2 \arctan\left(\frac{a}{2}\right) - \frac{a}{2} \right) \cdot \cos(2\theta_0) + \ln\left(1 + \frac{a^2}{4}\right) \cdot \sin(2\theta_0) \right] \end{aligned}$$

The next figures indicate the evolution of the Cauchy's stress components in the rigid body frame.

Figure 2. Normal stresses in the rigid body frame

Figure 3. Shear stresses in the rigid body frame

$$C_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha} = C_{\beta\beta\beta\beta} = 100010 \text{ MPa} ; C_{\alpha\alpha\beta\beta} = 6.8 \text{ MPa} ; C_{\alpha\beta\alpha\beta} = 4.4 \text{ MPa}, \theta_0 = 0^\circ$$

OUR STUDY

BASIC ASSUMPTIONS

The basic assumptions of our model are given as follows:

- ☛ on the macroscopic scale, the fabric has a plane of symmetry coinciding with the median plane of the fabric, and the material considered is a perfectly balanced fabric,
- ☛ the thickness of the fabric is small so that the stress vector components orthogonal to the median plane of the fabric are zero,
- ☛ deformations due to warping shrinkage are neglected. An average modulus is assigned to each of the warp and weft directions.
- ☛ The behaviour of the fabric is assumed to be orthotropic along the directions of the bisectors of the warp and weft roving. The components of the behaviour law then vary as functions of the relative rotation of these directions.

The latter assumption results from the kinematics study of two material segments, e.g. as in figure 4, which are initially perpendicular to an arbitrary initial position. This study compares the bisector rotation of the dihedron formed by these segments to the rotation of the rigid body derived from the polar decomposition. This assumption is permissible within the transformation range applicable for the studied process as it can be seen at the figure 5.

Figure 4. Rotation of the warp and weft yarns

Figure 5. Comparison between rotation of bisectors obtained from real rotations of warp and weft yarns and the rigid body rotation.

The variation of the behaviour law in the mobile coordinate system (e_α, e_β) corresponding to the rigid body rotation can then be monitored in order to ensure that the formulation is objective. Actually, one way to obtain an objective behaviour law for our material with material symmetry is to express it in a frame which rotates with the material. An orthotropic behaviour law will thus stay within it. Among those frames and according to our hypothesis, the rigid body frame, initially coinciding with the directions of the warp and weft yarns angle bisectors remains in coincidence throughout the transformation. Furthermore, as the deformations in the yarn directions are infinitesimal compared to the finite shear deformations in the fabric plane, the behaviour law remains orthotropic in this frame but evolves with the variation of the angle between warp and weft yarns. Only the variation of this orthotropy needs to be considered.

BEHAVIOUR LAW

We have chosen to work with a hypoelastic law, representative of the constitutive law of carbon yarns. The viscoelasticity of the resin is thus neglected and it is given an elastic modulus. We can write the law in the rotating frame as follow :

$$\dot{\bar{\sigma}} = [\mathbf{C}(\bar{\sigma})] \cdot [\bar{\mathbf{D}}] \quad \text{where } [\bar{\mathbf{D}}] \text{ is the strain rate, expressed in this frame.}$$

We will then use this frame together with the rigid body rotation to formulate strains and stresses at velocity to benefit from the objectivity of magnitudes manipulated in it, and we can write :

$$\bar{\sigma}(t + \Delta t) = \bar{\sigma}(t) + \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \dot{\bar{\sigma}}(\tau) d\tau \quad \text{in this rotating frame.}$$

In our incremental numeric formulation, taking the behaviour law variation into account, we assume that the rotation of the main elongation directions is zero on an increment. Furthermore, we assume that the behaviour law is constant for this increment. Note that this assumption is particularly justified for very small increments.

Therefore, we obtain:

$$\bar{\sigma}(t + \Delta t) = \bar{\sigma}(t) + \bar{C}_{\alpha\beta}(t) \cdot \Delta \bar{\mathbf{E}}^R$$

The $\bar{C}_{\alpha\beta}$ tensor of the behaviour law is calculated from the geometric positions of the two yarn directions which are up-dated at the end of the increment.

Let N_{warp} and N_{weft} be the respective direction vectors of a warp or weft yarn at the beginning of an increment. During this increment, those directions are transformed into n_{warp} and n_{weft} by :

$$n_{\text{warp}} = \frac{1}{\|\Delta \mathbf{F} \cdot N_{\text{warp}}\|} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{F} \cdot N_{\text{warp}} \quad \text{and} \quad n_{\text{weft}} = \frac{1}{\|\Delta \mathbf{F} \cdot N_{\text{weft}}\|} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{F} \cdot N_{\text{weft}} .$$

So we can express the angle between those two vectors and so recalculate the angle

$$\theta(t + \Delta t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\widehat{n_{\text{warp}}, n_{\text{weft}}} \right) \quad \text{between them and the bisector.}$$

The behaviour law is obtained for the next increment by integrating the local behaviour of the warp and weft networks (assumed to be independent) associated with the pre impregnation resin, across the thickness of the fabric, using the law $\bar{C}_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{h} \int (C_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{warp}}(-\theta) + C_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{weft}}(+\theta)) dz$ where $C_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{warp}}(-\theta)$ and $C_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{weft}}(+\theta)$ are the initial orthotropic homogenised behaviour laws for the warp or weft networks, expressed in a basis rotated from respectively $-\theta$ and $+\theta$. The rotation of the bisector being comparable to the rigid body rotation, the orthotropic behaviour law is objective.

BASIC TESTS

In order to validate our algorithm, we have implemented it in the ABAQUS industrial program by writing a "VUMAT" map, a subroutine used to define a specific behaviour law. Here below we present some results in comparison with a non up-dated material.

SIMPLE SHEAR TEST

This test has been described previously. The results obtained with a material which is a carbon satin are presented in figures 6-9.

Figure 6. Normal stresses in the rigid body frame

Figure 7. Shear stresses in the rigid body frame

Figure 8. Angle between the warp and weft directions

Figure 9. Resulting force in x and y directions

Behaviour law of one network of yarns :

$$C_{1111} = 100003 \text{ MPa} ; C_{2222} = 7.62 \text{ MPa} ; C_{1122} = 3.4 \text{ MPa} ; C_{1212} = 2.2 \text{ MPa}, \theta_0 = 0^\circ$$

The non up-dated normal stresses being insignificant compared to the up-dated stresses, they are not indicated in figure 6.

SIMPLE TENSILE TEST

This test has been performed in order to test the kinematic of deformation obtained with this algorithm. We have imposed a displacement on a sample with a 45° initial angle of the warp yarns, as the width of a real sample of fabric becomes 1/2 of the initial width. For this test the angle between yarns that we have to obtain is 41,4 degrees. We have found 42,2 degrees with our model and a width of 0.507, whereas the sample with non up-dated behaviour law is near 62 degrees with a width of 0.756 .

STAMPING OF A RECTANGULAR BOX

This test, which is classical for metallic materials, has been performed in order to validate our algorithm on a realistic case. It corresponds here to the preforming of fabrics in the RTM process. A punch pushes in a blank of fabric which is held up between a holder and the die. A pressure is applied on the holder. The initial angle of warp and weft yarns is respectively 0 and 90°.

A comparison has been made out with a test without updating of the behaviour law. The numerical results are satisfactory compared with the experimental tests which have been carried out by Gelin et al. [3].

Figure 10. Influence of the up-dating of the behaviour law

CONCLUSIONS

This study is the first part of a numerical model of the laying-up for non-developable composite parts. We must now introduce the viscoelastic behaviour in the constitutive equations to obtain an industrial aided design tool.

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